

DETERMINATION OF CROP COEFFICIENTS OF MAIZE FOR THE ESTIMATION OF CROP WATER USE

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ABSTRACT

The crop coefficients (k_c) of maize were determined for the growing season of month June to mid September. A hydraulic weighing lysimeter in National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM) was used to determine the crop evapotranspiration (ET_{crop}) for maize while meteorological data from the weather station at NCAM was used to compute reference crop evapotranspiration (ET_o) and potential evapotranspiration ET_p . Decade and monthly values of crop coefficients (k_c) for maize were obtained by determining daily values for and then averaged over ten day period and thirty day period for the decade and monthly values respectively. The crop coefficients (k_c) obtained for maize during the growing season ranged between 0.4 and 0.9. A high potential evapotranspiration value for maize was established from a high value of crop coefficient, while low values of temperature and sunlight hours resulted into low evaporation rate. It is evident from this research that the determination of crop evapotranspiration and the effects of weather conditions are essential for the estimation of crop water use.

KEYWORDS: hydraulic weighing lysimeter, evapotranspiration, crop coefficient.

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INTRODUCTION

Maize (*Zea Mays*), one of the most important food crops in Nigeria is grown for grain and forage and serves as important cereals both for human and animal consumption. It is widely grown in the Southern part of the country. However, the total hectare devoted to the production of this crop annually in the northern states is fast becoming significant. Adaptability of varieties in different climates varies widely. However, the plant breeders have come with suitable varieties for the different ecological zones where the crop is being cultivated.

Maize is an efficient user of water in terms of total dry matter production and among cereals; it is potentially the highest yielding grain crop. Water as the most important single factor limiting the production of maize has received global attention in the efforts to increase its production. Odofin et al., (2011) also affirmed that crop production demands not only efficient use of nutrients but also efficient and economic utilization of water especially when it is applied by irrigation. However, a good knowledge of water requirement is required for good water management in crop production. The knowledge of water requirements at the critical stages of crop growth is essential in the supply of water at the appropriate time and amount to crops in order to avoid serious reduction in crop yield especially under conditions of limited water supply.

To estimate the amount of water required for crops, it is necessary to know the amount supply by rainfall or irrigation, the amount used in evapotranspiration and the amount lost to deep percolation. One of the practicable methods for measuring evapotranspiration rate and determining the deep percolation is by using lysimeter. It is described as probably the best for determining the actual crop water requirement. However, the use of lysimeter for the determination of crop evapotranspiration (ET_{crop}) at various growing stages and computation of reference

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crop evapotranspiration (ET_o) by making use of developed empirical relationship would help to determine crop coefficients at various stages of crop growth (Benli et al., 2006; Miranda et al., 2006, Williams and Ayars, 2005). This will ultimately help to determine the actual crop water requirement at various stages of growth (Allen, et al. 1994; Nwa, 1994).

A number of crops are being grown under irrigation in the country at the moment and as irrigation facilities expand, additional crops will be advantageously grown under irrigation. What is lacking or is inadequate at the moment are the crop coefficients based on climatological condition of the area at the various growth stages of the crop (maize) in the country. Researchers have revealed that crop coefficient is related closely to crop type and management practice, which may influence plant development rate and yield (Allen et al., 1998; Williams and Ayars, 2005). The information obtained from crop coefficient of maize for the estimation of crop water use is necessary for the proper irrigation design, implementation and irrigation scheduling of maize (Duru and Adewumi, 1980).

The crop coefficient (k_c) is obtained by linking the actual crop evapotranspiration (ET_{crop}) to reference crop evapotranspiration (ET_o) as given in the equation below.

$$k_c = \frac{ET_{crop}}{ET_o} \quad (1)$$

Where: k_c is the crop coefficient, ET_{crop} is the crop evapotranspiration and ET_o is the reference crop evapotranspiration

There is a need for the use of a standard weighing lysimeter for the measurement of crop evapotranspiration which could be used to determine the crop coefficients and validate the crop water requirement obtained by empirical means for humid agro-ecological zone of Nigeria. A systematic investigation that attempts to assemble the various crop coefficients for various agro-ecological zones of Nigeria will be a great contribution to the food production effort in the country. However, there is a need to develop local coefficients instead of using assumed and generalized values because crop coefficient varies both with the crop characteristics and the climatic factors, among others.

The specific objectives for this research are to:

- (i) determine the crop evapotranspiration for maize by using the weighing lysimeter.
- (ii) determine the crop coefficients of maize and
- (iii) determine the potential evapotranspiration of maize.

METHODOLOGY

The accepted method of determining crop coefficient (k_c) is by relating the crop evapotranspiration (ET_{crop}) to the reference crop evapotranspiration (ET_o) as given in Eqn. 1. Assuming that the value of ET_o is reliable, then the reliability of the crop coefficient will depend on the accuracy of the ET_{crop} obtained from the lysimeter.

A buffer area of 100 m x 100 m was used on the lysimeter research field, which was planted with maize as on the lysimeter area of 3.24 m² (Adeogun et al., 1997). The lysimeter was located at the centre of the field with a uniformly cropped surface to provide a reasonable fetch. Measurements of ET_{crop} were taken from the lysimeter as well as meteorological data from the weather station at National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM). Daily lysimeter readings were obtained from the research field and the ET_{crop} was determined. The data for meteorological parameters required were obtained from NCAM weather station. These parameters which were recorded by the station on the daily basis were averaged over ten day and thirty day period chosen to correspond with the same decades and months over which lysimeter readings were taken. The averaged parameter values were used to compute ET_o and ET_p .

The crop water requirements for maize within the experimental field were calculated from the pan evaporation data obtained from meteorological station. The equation is given by FAO (1986) as found in Eqn. 2. The pan coefficient usually was taken as 0.75 (Michael, 1979; Stern, 1985; FAO, 1986). The adjusted Blanney-Criddle (ABC) equation (Eqn. 3) was developed by Fapohunda and Ude (1992) which was found to predict ET_p with satisfactory accuracy and therefore recommended for use in the tropics. This was employed to determine ET_p for maize.

The methods for calculating ET_o and ET_p from meteorological parameter are as follows:

- (I) Pan evaporation method.
(FAO, 1986)

$$ET_o = k_p \cdot E_{pan} \quad (2)$$

where ET_o is the reference crop evapotranspiration, k_p is the pan coefficient and E_{pan} is the pan evaporation.

- (II) Adjusted Blaney – Criddle (ABC) model for the tropic.
(Fapohunda and Ude, 1992)

$$ET_p = \frac{(37.846 - 0.254R_H)k_c k_t TP}{100} \quad (3)$$

where ET_p = Potential evapotranspiration (mm/day)
 k_t = (0.0173T-0.314) monthly temperature factor
 T = mean monthly temperature in °f
 P = monthly percent of daylight hours of the year
 R_H = Relative Humidity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tables 1 and 2 shows the values used in determining the various parameters used in computing reference crop evapotranspiration (ET_o) and crop coefficients (k_c). The crop evapotranspiration for maize (ET_{crop}) was determined directly from the measurement carried out on the hydraulic weighing lysimeter at NCAM, Ilorin. The values of k_c obtained from Tables 1 and 2 established the crop coefficients of maize for the first eleven decades and the three and half months of the growing season (June – mid September).

The crop evapotranspiration of maize throughout the growing season and the cumulative water use shows relatively lower values of evapotranspiration at the beginning of growing stages and increase during the period of rapid growth to a maximum and declining at maturity (Fig. 1). The short term fluctuation during the growing stages was as a result of variations in the prevailing weather conditions. For instance at a given relative humidity and high evaporation value, there are corresponding high values of ET_{crop} except at the initial growth stage such as sprouting to leaf formation. At this stage there was a low ET_{crop} value because of low leaf area of maize which influences the rate of transpiration of the crop. during the vegetative growth stage, the ET_{crop} increases to full maturity at leaf area of the crop, since there is enough leaf area to intercept sufficient solar energy to support or influence evapotranspiration.

Table 3 showed the meteorological parameter values used to compute the ET_p for maize for each month. The most important parameters that influence the potential evapotranspiration rate are temperature, sunshine hour and crop coefficient. At high values of temperature and sunshine hours, there are corresponding high values of ET_p . The only exception occurs in August where there were low values of temperature and sunshine hours, but yet with a high ET_p . The most important factor that responsible for this was the high value of crop coefficient which occurred as a result of high ET_{crop} within that period. The highest temperature occurred in June, causing

high evaporation rate which influence the ET_p value. Therefore ET_p of June is higher than that of September with equal crop coefficient.

The values of crop coefficient (k_c) obtained ranges from 0.4 to 0.9 at different period of growing stages. The variation in these values establishes the fact that the crop coefficient varies with stage of crop maturity and time of the year and most importantly, it is influenced by the prevailing weather condition (rainfall and temperature) at any given period of time.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

It is considered that the most important achievement of this work is that the determination of consumptive use of crops has been made easy by measuring ET_{crop} of any given crop by the use of the hydraulic weighing lysimeter at NCAM research field. This is possible as shown in the experiment carried out on maize during the growing season. Hence, the determination of k_c is possible by the calculation of ET_o using simple empirical formula with parameter data obtained from meteorological station, in conjunction with lysimeter measurement of ET_{crop} .

However, the establishment of k_c for other crops should be determined. And it is also recommended that the establishment of k_c should be carried out for the entire year as opposed to convectional growing season used in this study. Hence, the need for irrigation system for the research activities is highly essential in the centre. Through these activities, the lysimeter experiment should be continued and a verification of k_c for the same crop made to test and firmly establish consistency.

REFERENCES

- Adeogun, E. O.; E. U. Nwa; H. L. Musa and F.I. Idike, 1997. Design, Construction, Installation and Calibration of a Hydraulic Weighing Lysimeter at NCAM, Ilorin. *Journal of Agricultural Engineering and Technology* (1997), 5, 37-45.
- Allen, R. G.; Smith, M.; Pereira, L. S. and Perrier, A. 1994. An Update for the Calculation of Reference Evapotranspiration. *ICID Bulletin*. Vol.43(2):1-92.
- Allen, R.G., Pereira, L.S., Raes, D., Smith, M., 1998. Crop Evapotranspiration Guidelines for Computing Crop Water Requirements, Irrigation and Drain, Paper no. 56. FAO, Rome.
- Benli, B., Kodal, S., Ilbeyi, A., Ustun, H., 2006. Determination of evapotranspiration and basal crop coefficient of alfalfa with a weighing lysimeter. *Agric. Water Manage.* 81, 358–370.
- Duru, J. O. and J. K. Adewumi, 1980. Evapotranspiration potential to crop. *Proceedings, Nigerian Society of Agricultural Engineers* 4 : 120 – 136.
- FAO, 1986. Yield Response to Water. FAO Irrigation and Drainage Paper No 33:1-28.
- Fapohunda, H. O. and Ude, I. C. 1992. Estimating Potential Evapotranspiration from Tropical Climatological Data. *The Nigerian Engineer*, vol. 27(1) : 23 – 29.
- Michael, A. M. 1979. *Irrigation Theory and Practice*. Vikas Publishing House PVT Ltd. New Delhi Bombay Bangalore Calcutta Kanpur.
- Miranda, F.R., Gondim, R.S., Costa, C.A.G., 2006. Evapotranspiration and crop coefficients for Tabasco pepper (*Capsicum frutescens* L.). *Agric. Water Manage.* 82, 237–246.
- Nwa, E. U. , 1994. Appropriate Irrigation and Drainage Practices to Support the Index Crops for the Various Ecological Zones of Nigeria. Paper presented at the National Symposium on Water Resources and Rural Development, Kano State House of Assembly. 34pp.

Odofin, A. J., J. A. Oladiran, J. A. Oladipo and E. P. Wuya 2011. Determination of evapotranspiration and crop coefficients for bush okra (*Corchorus olitorius*) in a sub-humid area of Nigeria. *African Journal of Agricultural Research* Vol. 6(17): 3949-3953.

Stern, P. 1985. Small Scale Irrigation. A manual of low-cost water technology. 11/111 C Pub.: 69 – 141.

Williams, L.E., Ayars, J.E., 2005. Grapevine water use and the crop coefficient are linear functions of the shaded area measured beneath the canopy. *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 132, 201–211.

Table 1. Decade values of E_{pan} , ET_o , ET_{crop} and k_c .

Decade	E_{pan}	ET_o	ET_{crop}	k_c
1	53.2	40	16	0.4
2	54.2	41	19	0.5
3	58.8	44	25	0.6
4	54.8	41	25	0.6
5	51.0	39	14	0.4
6	48.1	36	23	0.6
7	31.9	24	21	0.9
8	43.2	32	30	0.9
9	54.0	40	31	0.8
10	41.5	31	22	0.7

Table 2. Monthly values of E_{pan} , ET_o , ET_{crop} and k_c .

Month	E_{pan}	ET_o	ET_{crop}	k_c
June	166.2	124.7	43.8	0.4
July	159.3	119.5	71.3	0.6
August	117.2	87.9	96.1	0.8
September	143.1	107.34	45	0.4

Table 3. Monthly values of ET_p from meteorological data.

Month	R_H	T (°f)	P (hr)	k_t	k_c	ET_p
June	0.87	85	6.31	1.16	0.4	94.7
July	0.86	81.1	4.03	1.11	0.6	81.9
August	0.86	79.8	3.63	1.07	0.8	128.3
September	0.87	81.0	4.49	1.08	0.4	59.1

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